

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BOTIR ZAKIROV'S SONGS IN POPULAR SINGING

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Abstract: Botir Zakirov occupies an important place in the history of Uzbek music as a pop singer. His songs enriched not only Uzbek folk music, but also modern pop genres. A successful combination of folk music and pop music can be seen in Zakirov's work. His songs played an important role in expressing deep meaning and feelings, expanding the means of musical expression. In this article, we talked about the role and importance of Botir Zakirov's songs in the art of pop singing.

Keywords: Botir Zakirov, founder of national pop singer, pop singer, Uzbek music, folk music, modern pop, musical harmony, singing art, musical heritage, Uzbek pop, emotion their expression, musical dramaturgy, means of musical expression.

Introduction:

Botir Zakirov is the founder of the Uzbek national pop singer. B. Zakirov is one of the first and brightest representatives of the Uzbek national pop music, and his creative heritage is of great importance in pop music. Zakirov's work brought new diversity, innovation and cultural richness to Uzbek music. His songs are of great importance for pop singers not only musically, but also aesthetically, culturally and spiritually. Botir Zakirov is an Uzbek pop singer and actor. He was awarded the title of People's Artist of Uzbekistan and is known for his bright creative work. Zakirov successfully combined Uzbek folk music and pop genres and made a great contribution to the development of modern music. Botir Zokirov showed his creative activity mainly through pop songs and musical performances. His work was distinguished by his unique voice and performance style. He performed many songs and is known as one of the greatest representatives of Uzbek music.

Motifs of Uzbek folk music occupy a significant place in B. Zakirov's work. He reworked and modernized many traditional Uzbek songs in the pop genre. His performance was often distinguished by its own drama and emotionality. Zakirov's most famous songs include "Uzbekistan", "Ko'qon Guli", "Last meeting" and many other works. These songs are distinguished by their deep meaning, lyricism and melody. His work has been a source of inspiration for many generations.

In many of his songs, Botir Zakirov showed the richness of national music by processing folk tunes and songs in a pop style. He combined national values with modern pop music and gave a new generation of singers the opportunity to get inspiration from national music and preserve it. This process contributed to the rise of national culture in the pop scene as well.

Botir Zakirov tried different musical genres and created new directions in his work. In addition to elements of traditional Uzbek music, modern pop styles are also combined in his songs. This inspired innovative approaches and experiments for new singers. The musical

diversity of Zakirov's songs allowed pop singers to expand their creativity and explore new musical possibilities.

Botir Zakirov's strong vocal skills and musical technique set high standards in pop singing. The complex vocal parts, delicate expression and skill of reflecting emotions in his songs became an example for the new generation of singers. Through Zakirov's songs, pop singers tried to develop their vocal techniques and increase their creative potential.

Botir Zakirov is one of the internationally known artists who brought Uzbek music to the world stage. Through his songs, Uzbek music gained international recognition. This encouraged young singers to show their art at the international level and make themselves known. Through Zakirov's songs, pop singers had the opportunity to develop international cultural relations and introduce their music to the world.

Botir Zakirov became a source of inspiration for many young singers with his creativity and personality. His stage culture, originality and love for his profession serve as an exemplary image for the new generation of singers. Zakirov's songs encourage young singers to express deeper meanings and feelings in their works, to pay great attention to stage culture.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that Botir Zakirov's songs are of great importance in pop singers, and through his work, the richness of national music, innovative approaches, vocal skills and international recognition are guiding pop singers. His songs serve to inspire young singers, develop their creative potential and promote national music on the world stage. Botir Zakirov's work is eternally important in pop music and creates a solid foundation for the new generation. Botir Zakirov's work has not lost its importance even today. His songs and performance greatly influenced the development of Uzbek pop music. Zakirov's musical legacy has been preserved as an integral part of Uzbek folk music and pop art. Botir Zakirov is a person who has taken an important place in Uzbek music and pop art with his bright and rich creative work. His creativity and art have been and will continue to be an inspiration to many generations.

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